

A STUDY OF PERCEPTION, USE AND CHALLENGES OF ELECTRONIC INFORMATION RESOURCES AMONG THE STUDENTS OF MANUU-CTE SRINAGAR

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to investigate the perception, use and challenges of The Electronic Information Resources among the students of MANUU-CTE Srinagar. A descriptive research design was adopted. A census sampling technique was used to collect the data from the students of session 2018-19 and 2019- 2020. The data gathered were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The results revealed that electronic information resources are used at different levels by respondents. It shows that user's perception influences use of electronic information resources. From the findings it is deduced that user's perception influences use of e-resources, while lack of awareness , training, unreliable internet connectivity, insufficient e-resources in various study areas, unavailability of e-resources on 24/7 and difficulty of identifying relevant information to meet user's needs are challenges hindering use of e-resources. The study concludes that librarians should acquire more e-resources to cover various study areas, create more awareness of e-resources at the library to change user's perception and introduce 24/7 internet services.

Key words: *Electronic Information Resources, user perception, MANUU-CTE Srinagar*

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INTRODUCTION

The 21st century brought several challenges to the library as a service unit in tertiary institutions since much emphasis is laid on information and communication technology (ICT). The use of ICT in academic libraries paved the way to the use of internet, automation services and provision of electronic information resources in library operation and services.

According to **Andreou** (2001), No academic library is considered as modern if it does not provide some basic electronic information resources such as: OPAC, CD-ROMS and internet facilities to its students. There is a growing demand on the use of electronic information resources (EIRs) in academic libraries. This is because of its dynamic nature, Interoperability

and flexibility compared to print resources. EIRs also known as e- resources come in different forms such as e-book, e-journal, e-dictionaries, e-magazines among others which are accessible via CD-ROMs, e-databases and the internet. Library information resources serve an important purpose in learning, teaching and research in any academic institution of higher learning. Effort is usually

made by libraries to acquire relevant information resources to meet the information needs of the library users. Library information resources are usually acquired through outright purchase or subscription and they are in both print and electronic formats.

Library users usually patronize databases that are authoritative, which provides information that is up to the minute, international in scope and accessible.

Availability of e-resources has changed what users actually read and use (Renwick, 2005).EIRs are acquired in libraries to complement existing library resources and to reduce pressure on print sources. They are easily disseminated since it can be duplicated, manipulated, copied, printed, shared and disseminated among library users .Igbo and Imo (2014) stated that a major advantage of EIRs is being able to share and distribute the resource.

According to **Oyedapo and Ojo** (2013), e-journal offers a range of potential advantages to libraries and users.

Most e-libraries have necessary facilities for the management, access and dissemination of EIRs. This may include power supply, information and communication technology infrastructure such as: computers, networking, servers, internet access, router and modem.

The need for library users to acquire skills in searching, accessing and retrieving of information in the library cannot be over emphasized .This will increase the user's confidence and use of library resources.

Bamedile , Omeluzor and Anandi (2013) advocated that as electronic journals are fast becoming more acceptable and usage is increasing ,it is pertinent for library users to attain high level of expertise or possibly learn to utilize them effectively. Before EIRs are broadly utilized in libraries ,print sources were the only means of disseminating academic information and research findings .However ,advancement in information and communication technology (ICT) enhances information services in libraries.

EIRs are dynamic among other library information resources. Due to its availability and accessibility in academic libraries, user's perception of the library has drastically changed. It has also increased patronage leading to provision of quality and satisfactory services to the library users.This study tends to investigate the perception. Use and challenges of electronic

information resources by the students of MANUU College for Teacher Education Srinagar.

REVIEW OF THE RELATED LITERATURE

Renwick(2005) conducted a study on the knowledge and use of electronic information resources by Medical Science Faculty at the university of West Indies .The study revealed that most of the respondents felt that they were competent users,83% claimed that they acquired skills through self-taught while many expressed a need for training.

Odongo and Okello-Obura (2013) in their study on electronic information resource utilization by students in Mbarara University library revealed that 63% of the respondents used internet search engines,13.5% used e-books ,11.6% used CD-ROM and 7.5% e-journals and 5.6% used scholarly databases .The study also showed that students perceive internet to be easier than other e-resources.

Adeniran (2014) conducted a study on usage of electronic resources by undergraduates at the Redeemer's University , Nigeria .Among the challenges encountered by the respondents is the large mass of irrelevant information, the need to filter the results from search, download delay, failure to find information ,inadequate or lack of search skills ,high cost of access, inaccessibility of some electronic resources, difficulties in navigating through electronic resource etc.

Ogbuiyi, etal.(2014) revealed that the accessibility and use of e-resources in Nigeria is faced with challenges

Literature revealed that frequent power failure ,poor internet connectivity and improper guidance on use of e- resources were the factors that militate against accessing e-resources.

Omeluzor (2015) examined faculty staff awareness and willingness to deposit research work in institutional repository in selected public and private universities in Nigeria. The findings showed that 58% and 50% of the respondents in private and public universities respectively indicated that poor information technology infrastructure development was a challenge to deposit research findings in institutional repository.

OBJECTIVES FOR THE PRESENT STUDY

1. To study the perception about the electronic information resources among the students of MANUU College for Teacher Education Srinagar.
2. To access the level of the usage of the electronic information resources by the students of MANUU College for Teacher Education Srinagar.
3. To study the challenges faced in the use of electronic information resources by the students of MANUU College for Teacher Education Srinagar.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study investigates the perception, use and challenges of electronic information resources among the students of MANUU-College for Teacher Education Srinagar. The study involved a descriptive survey design. A census sampling technique was used. The study population comprised of B.ED and M.ED students of session 2018-2020.

The choice of this group of students is because at the time of this study, they were fully engaged in research, presentations, class-work and other academic activities. Therefore, it is expected that they will utilize EIRs to support their research.

Questionnaire was the major instrument used for the data collection. The questionnaire was administered face to face to the respondents. Data collected were analyzed using frequency distribution and percentage.

ANALYSIS AND INTEPRETATION

Table 1: Perception of students about electronic information resources

S. No	Statement	Strongly Agreed	Agreed	Disagreed	Strongly Disagreed
a.	The EIRs is insufficient in my study area	39 (26.35%)	91 (61.49%)	18 (12.16%)	0 0.00
b.	The Internet sites and other databases are better than the library e-resources	39 (26.35%)	59 (39.86%)	50 (33.78%)	0 0.00
c.	Electronic information resources are				

	not well structured	11 (7.43%)	50 (33.78%)	68 (45.95%)	19 (12.84%)
d.	It takes time to search through the computer systems for e-books/e-journals.	14 (9.46%)	58 (39.19%)	67 (45.27%)	9 (6.08%)
e.	The e-resources are not 24/7 accessible.	57 (38.51%)	36 (24.32%)	51 (34.46%)	4 (2.70%)

Result in table 1 reveals that 87.84% of the respondents perceive the e-resources in their study area to be insufficient while 12.16% of the respondents are of a contrary view. 26.35% and 39.86% of the respondents perceive the internet sites and other databases to be better than the library subscribed e-resources while 33.78% of the respondents disagreed. It shows that 7.43% and 33.78% strongly agreed and agreed that EIRS are not well structured while majority i.e, 58.79% of the respondents strongly disagreed and disagreed that view. Result also reveal that 9.46% , 39.19% strongly agreed and agreed that searching through the computer system for e-book and e-journal is time consuming. It also indicated that 38.51% and 24.32% of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that e-resources in the library are not 24/7 accessible.

Table 2: Level of use of electronic information resources by respondents.

S. No	Electronic resources	Monthly	Bimonthly	Weekly	Daily	Occasionally	Not Used
a.	e-book	1 (0.68%)	0 (0.00%)	51 (34.46%)	0 (0.00%)	31 (20.95%)	65 (43.92%)
b.	e-journal	1 (0.68%)	0 (0.00%)	39 (26.35%)	10 (6.76%)	75 (50.68%)	23 (15.54%)
c.	e-database	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	37 (25.00%)	46 (31.08%)	51 (34.46%)	14 (9.46%)
d.	CD-ROM	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	14 (9.46%)	0 (0.00%)	47 (31.76%)	87 (58.78%)
e.	Web OPAC	0 (0.00%)	27 (18.24%)	16 (10.81%)	22 (14.86%)	14 (9.46%)	69 (46.62%)
f.	Repositories	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	7 (4.73%)	41 (27.70%)	91 (61.49%)	9 (6.08%)
g.	e-dictionaries	31 (20.95%)	16 (10.81%)	32 (21.62%)	51 (34.46%)	18 (12.16%)	0 (0.00%)

On the level of use of EIRs , result in the table 2 reveals that majority or 56.09% of the respondents use e- book at different time ,while 43.92% of the respondents never use e-book. On use of e-journal, it shows that that 50.68% of the respondents use it occasionally, 26.35% use it weekly,6.76% use it daily,0.68% use monthly while 15.54% never use it. Result also reveals that 25% use e-database weekly, 31.08% use it daily, 34.46% use it occasionally. On the use of CD-ROMs, 9.46% of the respondents use it weekly against 31.76% that use it occasionally and 58.78% of the respondents do not use it. Also ,result reveals that majority 46.62% of the respondents never use Web OPAC.A total of 18.24% use it bimonthly,10.81% use it weekly while 14.86% and 9.46% of the respondents use it daily and occasionally respectively. On the use of repositories ,result shows that 61.49% of the respondents use it occasionally, 27.70% use daily, 4.73% use it weekly while 6.08% of the respondents have never used it. Result shows that e-dictionaries attracted 20.95% users monthly, 10.81% users bimonthly,21.62% users weekly, 34.46% users daily and 12.16% users used it occasionally. It means that e-dictionaries resource was used at all times by the respondents compared to other e-resources.

Table 3: Challenges faced by the respondents in the use of electronic information resources .

S.No	Statement	Strongly Agreed	Agreed	Strongly Disagreed	Disagreed
a.	Lack of awareness	62 (41.89%)	41 (27.70%)	45 (30.41%)	0 (0.00%)
b.	Lack of training in using e-resources	24 (16.22%)	74 (50.00%)	50 (33.78%)	0 (0.00%)
c.	Unreliable Internet connectivity (access)	57 (38.51%)	38 (25.68%)	34 (22.97%)	19 (12.84%)
d.	Insufficient e-resources in my field of study	75 (50.68%)	16 (10.81%)	45 (30.41%)	12 (8.11%)
e.	Difficulty in identifying relevant information to meet my information needs	59 (39.86%)	38 (25.68%)	51 (34.46%)	0 (0.00%)

Results in the table 3 reveal that 41.89% and 27.70% of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that lack of awareness constitute a hindrance to the use of EIRS in academic libraries. It also shows that 16.22% and 50% of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that lack of training on the use of e-resources is a hindrance while 33.78% of the respondents disagreed. On reliability of Internet connection ,result shows that 38.51% and 25.68% of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that unreliable internet connectivity is a challenge to assessing e-

resources in the library while 35.81% of the respondents disagreed. Result also revealed that 50.68% and 10.81% of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that there are insufficient e-resources in their field of study. The result further shows that 39.86% and 25.68% of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that identifying relevant information to meet user's information needs is a challenge.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study showed users perception and the level of electronic information resources usage as well as challenges faced in academic libraries. It is evident in this study that use of e-resources has increased compared to its usage in recent past, which means that users' perception of the resources has drastically changed.

Result from the study indicated that user's perception influences level of electronic information resources usage in academic libraries. Use of e-resources is highly dependent on availability of Internet connection; therefore, academic libraries must try to create hotspots and Wi-Fi in addition to the networked computers to enable users to have access to e-resources.

Usage of e-resources in academic libraries is affected by some challenges which are not insurmountable, this include lack of awareness, lack of training, unreliable Internet connection and insufficient e-resources in some field of study. Therefore, librarians must endeavor to create awareness of available e-resources, training of all level of users, improve Internet access and ensure subsequent subscription to relevant e-resources and databases in different fields of study. That will definitely change the perception that users have about the library and they will be encouraged in using e-resources.

In line with the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Electronic information resources should be made accessible on a 24/7 bases. This will encourage usage as well as changing users' perception of IRs in academic libraries.
2. Training of all level of users (students, staff, and researchers) must be taken seriously to ensure that they make adequate use of the resources.
3. Library must carry out an extensive awareness campaign using every available opportunity such as user education, use of library class, congregational meeting, orientation, seminar, workshop, libraries social media page among others to sensitize users about e-resources in the library. This will create awareness of the available information resources in the library.
4. Librarians should assist library users on possible ways to navigate through e-resources to achieve better search results.
5. Libraries must provide a catalogue of subscribed electronic information resources to enable

users to easily identify and access relevant e-resources tailored to their information need.

6. Libraries should carry out needs assessment to identify users' information needs in order to subscribe to e-resources that will be useful in their field of study.

7. Internet connectivity must be improved in academic libraries for effective use of electronic information resources by library users.

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